

DYNAMICS OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY INDICATORS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS ACTIVITY.

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is one of the most common systemic rheumatic diseases, characterized by inflammation of the synovial membrane of the joints, destruction of cartilage and bone tissue, and the development of extra-articular manifestations [1]. The disease, as a rule, has a progressive course, leading to early disability and a reduction in life expectancy of patients [2]. The role of infectious agents in the development of RA, such as the Epstein -Barr virus, retroviruses, rubella viruses, herpes, parvovirus B19, cytomegalovirus, mycoplasma, has been studied for a long time [4]. A clear association of the disease with the carriage of HLA-DR4 and HLA-DR1 antigens indicates a genetic predisposition to the development of RA [3]. However, the etiology of RA is still unknown, and its treatment is one of the most complex problems in rheumatology.

Relevance of the problem. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is one of the most common systemic rheumatic diseases, characterized by inflammation of the synovial membrane of the joints, destruction of cartilage and bone tissue, and the development of extra-articular manifestations [1]. The disease, as a rule, has a progressive course, leading to early disability and a reduction in life expectancy of patients [2]. The role of infectious agents in the development of RA, such as the Epstein -Barr virus, retroviruses, rubella viruses, herpes, parvovirus B19, cytomegalovirus, mycoplasma, has been studied for a long time [4]. A clear association of the disease with the carriage of HLA-DR4 and HLA-DR1 antigens indicates a genetic predisposition to the development of RA [3]. However, the etiology of RA is still unknown, and its treatment is one of the most complex problems in rheumatology. Despite numerous approaches to RA therapy, this disease still has an unfavorable risk of early disability and long-term prognosis [2]. 50% of patients with this disease become disabled within five years, and 10% within the first two years of the disease [4]. Chronic inflammation increases the risk of other diseases (atherosclerotic vascular disease, increased susceptibility to intercurrent infections, etc.). According to prospective studies, survival in some patients with RA approaches that of insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, severe atherosclerotic coronary artery disease, and stage III-IV lymphogranulomatosis [2]. The average life expectancy of patients with RA is reduced by 7 years in men and by 3 years in women [1].

The effectiveness of therapy is significantly higher in the initial period of the disease, when autoimmune mechanisms have not yet fully formed and pannus, the morphological basis of joint destruction, is absent [1]. It is in the early stages of RA that inflammation peaks, joint destruction progresses, and bone mineral density (BMD) loss is greatest [2]. Aggressive basic therapy in the early stages of RA is justified by the desire to persistently suppress the active immune-inflammatory process and thereby prevent subsequent joint destruction [4].

In addition to the use of basic drugs, the maximum effect of which develops gradually, the use of glucocorticoids (GC) is theoretically justified. However, the results of clinical use of GCs are highly controversial, and there are arguments for and against their use [1]. Arguments "for" include the rapid suppression of inflammatory symptoms (clinical and laboratory), improved quality of life of patients, and therefore a possible protective effect on BMD, primarily in the femoral neck, and a slowdown in radiologically detectable progression of joint destruction [4]. Arguments "against" the use of PS include their adverse effects: the possibility of an increased risk of gastropathy (especially with concomitant use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) and osteoporotic fractures, which are especially clearly manifested when high doses are prescribed over a long period of time [3].

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of low-dose PS (no more than 10 mg per day) in combination with disease-modifying drugs in early rheumatoid arthritis (RA) on clinical and laboratory activity, progression of joint destruction, and bone mineral density.

Study objectives: To determine the possibility of improving the clinical manifestations of RA and reducing laboratory parameters (assessed according to the criteria recommended by EULAR and ACR) using low doses of GC. To study the effect of low doses of GC on the progression of joint destruction.

Study results. Low doses of GCs, administered in combination with disease-modifying drugs, significantly reduce clinical and laboratory manifestations of RA activity (duration of morning stiffness, CRP and IL-6 levels). Treatment efficacy according to ACR criteria was significantly higher in the low-dose GC group. By month 12 of treatment, more patients meeting ACR 70 were identified in the prednisolone and methotrexate group than in the methotrexate-only group ($p < 0.05$). Taking low doses of GC significantly slows down the rate of occurrence of erosions in the hands and feet: new erosions in the group of patients receiving prednisolone and methotrexate by the end of the year of observation were detected in 3 patients, in the group receiving only methotrexate - in 11 ($p < 0.05$).

In early RA, occurring with high activity, there is a decrease in the BMD of the axial skeleton: in the lumbar spine for the group of patients receiving prednisolone and methotrexate, it was 2.7%, in the femoral neck - 4.9%; for the group of patients receiving methotrexate - 2.3% and 2.1%, respectively.

A significant correlation was found between the progression of erosive arthritis and the mean values of IL-6 ($R=0.66$) and CRP ($R=0.64$) in the group of patients receiving only methotrexate ($p < 0.05$). The baseline level of IL-6 significantly negatively correlated ($R=-0.36$) with the absolute values of BMD of the femoral neck at the beginning of the study in both groups ($SR < 0.05$).

Conclusions. No significant differences were found between groups in the rate of decline in axial skeletal BMD or the dynamics of bone metabolism markers by the end of the year. In

early RA, an increase in the level of the resorption marker ((^α-fragment of the carboxyterminal telopeptide of type 1 collagen) and bone tissue formation (N-Mid osteocalcin) is a predictor of decreased axial skeletal BMD and radiographic disease progression.

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